
Implementation of Bojonegoro Regency Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Community Tranquility in the Regulation of Street Vendors in Bojonegoro District

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the implementation of Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2015 in regulating street vendors in Bojonegoro Regency and to identify key factors that shape the gap between regulatory objectives and practical outcomes within a decentralized governance framework. The research employs a qualitative descriptive design. Data were collected through in-depth interviews, non-participant observation, and document analysis involving *Satpol PP* officials and street vendors. The analysis is guided by Van Meter and Van Horn's policy implementation model, focusing on policy standards and objectives, resources, implementing agency characteristics, implementer disposition, inter-organizational communication, and the social, economic, and political environment. The findings indicate that policy standards are clear and institutional capacity is relatively adequate, supported by systematic socialization, staged enforcement, and structured organizational arrangements. However, implementation remains only partially effective due to strong external constraints. Economic insecurity among street vendors, limited political engagement, and low social acceptance significantly undermine compliance and lead to recurring violations. The study concludes that effective public order policy implementation depends not only on administrative capacity but also on the alignment of policy demands with socio-economic and political realities. Strengthening participatory approaches and livelihood-sensitive strategies is essential for more sustainable outcomes.

KEYWORDS: Policy Implementation, Public Order, Street Vendors, Local Governance, Satpol PP.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Decentralization has become a defining feature of contemporary public administration, particularly in countries seeking to enhance governance responsiveness, policy relevance, and democratic accountability at the local level (Faguet, 2014; Hidayat et al., 2025; Smoke, 2015). By transferring authority from central to regional governments, decentralization is expected to improve service delivery and enable policies that are more closely aligned with local socio-economic conditions. Nevertheless, the effectiveness of decentralization is not determined solely by formal regulatory frameworks, but by the capacity of local institutions to implement policies consistently and responsively in practice (Aulia, 2025; Hoesein & Rahayu, 2022; Shrestha & Hankla, 2025).

In Indonesia, decentralization is institutionalized through regional autonomy, which grants local governments broad authority to regulate governmental affairs within the framework of a unitary state (Budijaya & Heryanto, 2024; Kurniawan et al., 2024; Usman, 2002). One of the key instruments supporting this authority is the regional regulation (*Peraturan Daerah/Perda*), which functions as a normative foundation for governing public order, social behavior, and local development. Public order and community tranquility are classified as mandatory governmental affairs delegated to regional governments, allowing them to regulate the technical implementation of these responsibilities through local legislation (Hidayatulloh & Murdoko, 2025; Syaprianto et al., 2023). A persistent challenge in this governance context is regulating informal economic activities, particularly street vending. Street vendors (*Pedagang Kaki Lima/PKL*) play a crucial role in creating employment and strengthening local economic resilience, especially in regions with limited formal job opportunities (Anwar, 2024; Sattuo et al., 2025). However, their activities frequently conflict with regulations governing the use of public spaces, traffic management, sanitation, and environmental order. This tension

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places local governments in a difficult position, requiring them to balance public order objectives with social justice and livelihood protection (Rahayu et al., 2025).

In Bojonegoro Regency, this responsibility is formalized through Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Community Tranquility, which includes provisions on business order (*tertib usaha*). The regulation prohibits commercial activities in public spaces, such as sidewalks, green lanes, and public roads, unless authorized in advance. Enforcement of this regulation is primarily carried out by the Civil Service Police Unit (*Satuan Polisi Pamong Praja/Satpol PP*). Despite the clarity of the regulatory framework, empirical evidence indicates persistent implementation challenges, including weak communication between enforcement officers and street vendors, low compliance, insufficient provision of alternative trading locations, and recurring violations of public space regulations.

From a theoretical perspective, this study adopts the policy implementation model developed by Van Meter & Van Horn (1975), which conceptualizes implementation outcomes as being shaped by six interrelated variables: policy standards and objectives, resources, characteristics of implementing agencies, implementers' dispositions, inter-organizational communication, and the surrounding social, economic, and political environment. This framework is particularly relevant for analyzing public order policies, as their effectiveness depends not only on legal clarity but also on enforcement capacity, coordination, and societal acceptance.

Previous studies have examined the implementation of public order regulations across various regions of Indonesia. Wicaksono (2016) found that the implementation of public order policies in Nganjuk Regency was constrained by limited human resources, weak inter-agency coordination, and an unsupportive social environment. Wiyoto (2024), in his study on the implementation of street vendor arrangement policies at Taman Bungkul, Surabaya, found that policy implementation had not been fully effective due to multiple constraints, including weak communication between *Satpol PP* and street vendors, limited financial resources, inconsistent implementer commitment, and socio-economic resistance from vendors related to security and income loss following relocation. Similarly, Permana et al. (2023), in their study on the implementation of street vendor control policies in Bandung City, revealed that enforcement efforts were undermined by the absence of firm sanctions, institutional inconsistency among government agencies, and contradictory practices such as the continued collection of retribution fees from vendors operating in prohibited areas. While these studies share similarities with the present research in terms of policy focus and qualitative methodology, they differ in theoretical orientation and regional context. Unlike prior studies, this research applies Van Meter and Van Horn's policy implementation framework to offer a more integrated analysis of structural, institutional, and environmental factors shaping public order policy implementation.

Based on these considerations, this study aims to analyze the implementation of Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Community Tranquility in Bojonegoro Regency, with a specific focus on the regulation of street vendors. By examining key implementation variables and contextual constraints, this research seeks to explain the gap between regulatory intent and practical outcomes and to deepen understanding of policy implementation challenges in decentralized governance systems.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a qualitative descriptive research design to examine the implementation of Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Community Tranquility in Bojonegoro Regency, with a particular focus on the regulation of street vendors. Qualitative research is appropriate for exploring social phenomena in their natural settings and for understanding meanings, processes, and interactions from the perspectives of involved actors (Moleong, 2012). A descriptive approach is used to systematically portray empirical conditions and implementation dynamics without manipulating the research setting (Sugiyono, 2022). The research was conducted in Bojonegoro Regency, East Java. Data collection took place at the Office of the Civil Service Police Unit (*Satpol PP*) as the primary implementing agency, as well as in several public spaces where street vendors operate, including Bojonegoro City Square and major roads within Bojonegoro District. These locations were selected purposively to capture both institutional and field-level implementation practices (Akintola et al., 2024).

Data were obtained from primary and secondary sources. Primary data consisted of verbal accounts and observed actions derived from in-depth interviews and field observations. Secondary data included official documents, local regulations, institutional reports, and photographic documentation related to street vendor control and public order enforcement. In qualitative research, words and actions constitute the main data source, while documents function as supporting evidence (Chand, 2025; Moleong, 2012; Sugiyono, 2022). Informants were selected using purposive sampling, based on their direct involvement in or experience with policy implementation. The composition of informants is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Research Informants

No	Informant Category	Position / Description
1	Government Officials	Head of Division / Section of Guidance, Supervision, and Counseling, <i>Satpol PP</i> Bojonegoro
2	Law Enforcement Officers	Officers from Investigation and Enforcement Units, <i>Satpol PP</i>
3	Street Vendors (PKL)	Street vendors operating in public spaces within Bojonegoro District

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

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The analytical framework of this study is based on Van Meter & Van Horn's (1975) policy implementation model, which conceptualizes implementation performance through six interrelated variables:

1. Policy standards and objectives, referring to clarity and consistency of regulatory goals.
2. Resources, including human, financial, and time resources.
3. Characteristics of implementing agencies, covering formal and informal actors involved.
4. Implementers' disposition, reflecting attitudes, commitment, and responsiveness of enforcement officers.
5. Inter-organizational communication, particularly coordination among agencies.
6. Social, economic, and political environment, influencing public acceptance and compliance.

Data were collected through three main techniques, namely non-participant observation, semi-structured interviews, and documentation. Observation was conducted to examine enforcement practices, street vendor activities, and interactions between vendors and enforcement officers, allowing the researcher to capture real-time behavioral patterns and contextual conditions (Sugiyono, 2022). Semi-structured interviews were carried out using an interview guide to maintain analytical focus while providing flexibility for probing, thereby enabling an in-depth exploration of actors' perceptions, experiences, and implementation challenges (Moleong, 2012). Documentary analysis complemented these techniques through the examination of local regulations, institutional records, enforcement reports, and visual documentation to corroborate findings from interviews and observations.

Data credibility was strengthened through source triangulation and prolonged engagement by systematically comparing information obtained from interviews, observations, and documentary sources, as well as by sustaining field involvement to verify data consistency and deepen contextual understanding (Lim, 2025). Data analysis followed the interactive model proposed by Miles and Huberman, which comprises three interrelated and concurrent processes: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing or verification (Miles et al., 2014). Data reduction was carried out through systematic coding and categorization of field data, followed by narrative presentation to identify patterns and relationships. Conclusions were developed iteratively and continuously verified against empirical evidence to ensure analytical rigor and validity.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The implementation of Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Tranquility reflects the inherent complexity of local public policy processes. In policy studies, policy formulation—particularly at the local level—is widely recognized as a challenging endeavor; however, the implementation stage often presents even greater difficulties. This complexity arises because policy implementation is not merely a technical process but involves continuous interaction between target groups and bureaucratic actors responsible for enforcement. Public policy assumes the existence of shared public spaces in which collective activities take place and are therefore subject to regulation or government intervention. In this context, Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2015 represents the Bojonegoro Regency Government's effort to regulate public space and promote a safe, orderly, and peaceful local environment.

As a critical phase of the policy cycle, implementation functions as the link between policy formulation and its social consequences. The effectiveness of public policy depends not only on the clarity of its objectives but also on how it is translated into concrete actions on the ground. Despite having been in force for approximately seven years, the implementation of this regulation continues to face significant obstacles. This study investigates these challenges through in-depth interviews and field observations, employing the policy implementation framework proposed by Van Meter and Van Horn. This model emphasizes six interrelated elements influencing implementation outcomes: policy standards and objectives, resources, characteristics of implementing agencies, implementers' dispositions, inter-organizational communication and enforcement activities, and the broader economic, social, and political environment. These dimensions provide an analytical lens for understanding the gap between regulatory intent and practical outcomes in the enforcement of public order policies in Bojonegoro Regency.

1) Policy standards and objectives

The performance of policy implementation can largely be evaluated based on the clarity and realism of policy standards and objectives. If the policy's goals are overly ambitious or disconnected from the social and cultural context of implementers, achieving successful outcomes becomes challenging. Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Tranquility was found to have reasonably realistic objectives, particularly regarding the regulation of street vendors by the Bojonegoro Civil Service Police Unit (*Satpol PP*).

In practice, the implementers actively conduct both direct and indirect socialization of the regulation. Indirect socialization includes the placement of prohibition signs to inform the public of restricted vending areas. The aim is to reach all community members, not only those in Bojonegoro District, since the policy targets all societal layers. As stated by the Head of the Guidance, Supervision, and Socialization Section of *Satpol PP*:

"Before we carry out street vendor control, we provide socialization in the form of advisories to vendors to move to locations permitted by the Regent. In addition, we conduct indirect socialization by issuing warning letters and placing prohibition signs."

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Similarly, a field officer explained:

“We perform our duties according to our official functions and established policies. Vendors are first given direct advisories and we also place prohibition signs. Only if these are ignored do we take further action.”

From the vendor perspective, socialization efforts were acknowledged:

“Indeed, Satpol PP has provided advisories and guidance, and I have also noticed the prohibition signs in restricted areas.”

Table 2. Socialization Activities of Regional Regulation

Socialization Frequency	1 Week	1 Month	1 Year
Number of Activities	3	12	144

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

Despite these systematic socialization efforts, the policy’s intended impact on street vendor compliance remains limited. As noted by the Head of the Guidance, Supervision, and Socialization Section:

“The aim of this policy is to regulate public order by controlling street vendors to ensure that Bojonegoro District remains orderly and comfortable for residents. However, many vendors continue to violate the regulations by vending in prohibited areas.”

Vendors reported economic constraints as a reason for non-compliance:

“Although Satpol PP provides advisories, I need to earn a living for my family. Moving to a new location would reduce my income, so I return to my original spot.”

Based on Van Meter & Van Horn's (1975) implementation framework, the policy standards and objectives of Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2015 are clearly articulated and implementers demonstrate consistent adherence to procedural requirements.

However, the effectiveness of implementation is constrained by characteristics of target groups—here, street vendors whose economic motivations limit compliance. This aligns with Van Meter and Van Horn’s argument that successful implementation requires congruence between policy goals, implementer capacity, and target group behavior; even well-designed policies may face limited impact if implementers’ efforts are counteracted by non-cooperative target populations.

2) Resources

The success of policy implementation largely depends on the effective utilization of available resources, which include human, financial, and time resources. Human resources constitute the most critical factor, as the quality and competence of implementers directly influence the execution of the policy. For Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Tranquility, the Civil Service Police Unit (*Satpol PP*) serves as the primary implementing agency.

a. Human resources

Interviews with the Head of the Guidance, Supervision, and Socialization Section indicated:

“The human resources within Satpol PP are adequate. Educational backgrounds range from high school (SMA) to bachelor’s (S1) and master’s degrees (S2), enabling them to perform their duties effectively.”

This assessment was confirmed by the Subdivision of General Affairs and Personnel:

“Our personnel are sufficiently qualified, with many holding SMA, S1, and even S2 degrees. This allows each subunit to function according to its respective responsibilities and tasks.”

Table 3. Satpol PP Staff by Education Level

No	Position	SMA	S1	S2
1	Head of <i>Satpol PP</i>	–	1	1
2	Secretary	1	–	1
3	Public Order and Community Tranquility Division	–	1	1
4	Subdivision of Finance	1	–	1
5	Law Enforcement Division	–	1	1
6	Subdivision of Programs and Reports	–	1	1
7	Subdivision of General Affairs and Personnel	1	–	1
8	Community Protection Unit Section	–	1	1
9	Human Resource Section <i>Satpol PP</i>	–	1	1
10	Cooperation Section	–	1	1
11	Investigation and Inquiry Section	1	–	1
12	Operations and Control Section	–	1	1
13	Guidance, Supervision, and Socialization Section	–	1	1
14	Staff	5	–	5
15	Members	64	1	–
Total		64	13	6

Source: Dara processed by researchers (2026)

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b. Financial resources

Financial resources are essential to complement human capacity. According to the Head of Guidance, Supervision, and Socialization:

“Currently, the financial resources are sufficient for enforcement activities. The budget primarily covers fuel for vehicles, and no additional funds are required since the available equipment is adequate for dismantling illegal vending areas.”

This indicates that financial resources do not pose a significant constraint to the implementation process.

c. Time resources

Time allocation also influences implementation effectiveness. A field officer explained:

“We strive to achieve the policy objectives continuously. As long as violations persist, we carry out enforcement. However, time is limited because our duties extend beyond controlling street vendors to other responsibilities within Satpol PP.”

Despite adequate human and financial resources, limited time hampers the intensity of enforcement activities, resulting in persistent violations by some vendors.

Based on Van Meter & Van Horn's (1975) implementation framework, the findings suggest that *Satpol PP* possesses sufficient human and financial resources to carry out the policy. However, the limited availability of time reduces the overall effectiveness of enforcement. According to the framework, successful implementation depends not only on resource availability but also on the ability to align implementer capacity with policy objectives and the demands of target groups. In this case, even with competent personnel and adequate funding, insufficient time allocation constrains the intensity of enforcement, illustrating the interdependence of resources in achieving policy goals.

3) Characteristics of implementing agencies

The characteristics of implementing agents encompass bureaucratic structure, organizational norms, and the patterns of relationships within the bureaucracy, all of which significantly affect policy implementation. According to Agustino (2006), attention to both formal and informal organizational structures is essential for understanding how public policy is executed. The selection and organization of implementing agents should align with the nature of the policy: strict, disciplined enforcement may be required for policies targeting fundamental behavior change, while other policies may require agents who are democratic and persuasive. Additionally, the geographic scope of policy implementation influences the number of agents involved; broader coverage requires larger, better-coordinated teams.

In the case of Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Tranquility, the Civil Service Police Unit (*Satpol PP*) serves as the primary implementing agency. Interviews with the Head of the Guidance, Supervision, and Socialization Section revealed the following:

“We ensure that all personnel are fully briefed on the objectives of the operation, the number of staff required, and overall readiness. We carefully select suitable personnel to ensure effective performance.”

Another officer explained:

“We conduct enforcement politely but firmly. In cases of serious violations, sanctions are applied to create a deterrent effect and ensure that the regulation is respected.”

These statements indicate that the *Satpol PP* has established clear norms and procedures for organizing personnel, assigning responsibilities, and applying sanctions, which are critical for achieving policy objectives.

Table 4. Staffing and Role Assignment in *Satpol PP* for Street Vendor Enforcement

Position	Number of Personnel	Notes on Role/Responsibility
Head of <i>Satpol PP</i>	1	Oversees all operations
Guidance, Supervision, and Socialization Section	3	Conducts briefings, monitors enforcement, and supervises personnel
Enforcement Officers	15	Direct enforcement, socialization, and sanctioning
Support Staff	5	Administrative and logistical support

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

Based on Van Meter & Van Horn (1975) implementation framework, the alignment between policy objectives and the characteristics of implementing agents is essential for effective execution. In this case, the *Satpol PP* demonstrates a well-structured organization with clearly defined norms, appropriate personnel selection, and a balance of persuasive and disciplinary strategies. These characteristics facilitate policy enforcement; however, the success of implementation still depends on agents' ability to interact effectively with target populations and adapt to situational challenges. This finding underscores Van Meter and Van Horn's proposition that organizational characteristics and the appropriateness of agent attributes are critical determinants of implementation outcomes.

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4) Implementers' disposition

The disposition of implementing agents significantly affects the effectiveness of public policy implementation. Agents' acceptance or resistance to policy determines the degree to which policy objectives are achieved. This is particularly relevant in top-down policies, such as Regional Regulation of Bojonegoro Regency Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Tranquility, where policy decisions are formulated at higher administrative levels and may not fully reflect local needs or conditions. The Civil Service Police Unit (*Satpol PP*), specifically the Guidance, Supervision, and Socialization Section, is responsible for implementing street vendor regulation.

An interview with the Head of Guidance, Supervision, and Socialization Section revealed:

"Satpol PP personnel carry out their duties according to their respective functions. Some focus on enforcement, others provide guidance to vendors. We do not stop at warnings; if vendors ignore instructions, we confiscate their goods and require them to come to the office with identification documents to retrieve them. During retrieval, we provide guidance to ensure vendors do not return to prohibited areas. Nevertheless, some vendors still return to restricted locations."

The implementers' actions are further supported by the enforcement officers' roles as shown in Table 5:

Table 5. Street Vendor Enforcement Coordinators

Name/Position	Duties
Head of Guidance, Supervision, and Socialization Section	Provides guidance to vendors during retrieval of confiscated goods
Enforcement Officers	Enforce regulations against vendors who do not comply with the law

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

From the vendors' perspective, the enforcement process is acknowledged but constrained by economic needs. One vendor explained: *"Before enforcement, we are given warnings, which sometimes prompts us to try selling elsewhere. But eventually, we return to our original location to earn a living."*

Another vendor stated:

"After enforcement, we are asked to come to the Satpol PP office to retrieve our goods and receive guidance. However, I rely on selling here to support my family, and if my goods are confiscated, I cannot earn a living."

These findings indicate that the disposition of implementers is generally positive and professional, with personnel carrying out their responsibilities according to regulations while balancing enforcement with guidance. However, compliance among street vendors remains a challenge due to economic pressures.

According to Van Meter & Van Horn (1975), the disposition of implementers—including their willingness to accept and actively carry out policy—is a crucial determinant of successful implementation. In this case, *Satpol PP* personnel demonstrate high levels of commitment and adherence to formal procedures, combining enforcement with guidance to achieve policy objectives. Nonetheless, the persistence of violations by vendors illustrates that even highly committed implementers may encounter limits imposed by target group behaviors and socioeconomic constraints, highlighting the interdependence of implementer disposition and contextual realities in policy implementation outcomes.

5) Inter-organizational communication

Effective coordination is a critical mechanism in public policy implementation. Well-established communication among involved actors reduces implementation errors and minimizes resistance during execution. Policy implementation inherently requires the involvement of multiple actors, even when a single agency acts as the primary implementer. Without adequate coordination and communication, the presence of multiple supporting actors alone is insufficient to ensure that policy objectives are achieved.

In the context of street vendor regulation in Bojonegoro Regency, the Civil Service Police Unit (*Satuan Polisi Pamong Praja/Satpol PP*) functions as the main implementing agency responsible for maintaining public order and enforcing regional regulations. Effective communication between *Satpol PP* and street vendors is therefore essential to reduce implementation barriers and enhance policy compliance.

To examine inter-organizational communication practices, the researcher conducted an in-depth interview with the Head of the Division of Guidance, Supervision, and Public Outreach of the Bojonegoro Regency *Satpol PP*. He stated:

"Prior to conducting enforcement actions against street vendors, Satpol PP carries out socialization activities in the form of appeals, encouraging vendors to relocate their businesses to designated areas. We also issue written warnings on a regular basis. Socialization is conducted three times per week, twelve times per month, and a total of 144 times per year. We understand that street vendors rely on their businesses for livelihood, and therefore we strive to carry out our duties in a humane and professional manner."

Similarly, an enforcement officer explained:

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“We conduct enforcement strictly according to our assigned duties and functions. Street vendors are given prior warnings and appeals. If these warnings are ignored, enforcement actions are taken as a last resort.”

These statements indicate that communication efforts were systematically implemented through repeated direct socialization activities. Officers visited vendor locations to convey information regarding permitted trading areas and regulatory obligations. The frequency of these activities is summarized in Table 6.

Table 6. Frequency of Regional Regulation Socialization Activities

Socialization Period	Frequency
Per Week	3 times
Per Month	12 times
Per Year	144 times

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

In addition to information obtained from implementers, street vendors’ perspectives further illustrate the effectiveness of communication. One food vendor stated:

“Socialization was indeed carried out by Satpol PP, and the communication was conducted politely. I received socialization three times, which eventually encouraged me to relocate my business to Kartini Street.”

However, not all vendors responded positively. Another vendor expressed economic concerns:

“It is true that appeals and socialization were conducted by Satpol PP. However, I need to earn a living to support my family. Although a new location has been provided, I am worried that my income will decrease if I move.”

These findings indicate that while communication mechanisms functioned effectively in terms of information delivery, economic considerations remained a major factor influencing vendor compliance.

Satpol PP’s communication strategies included formal appeals, signage installation, and written warnings, as summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Forms of Appeals Issued by Satpol PP

No	Appeals
1	Providing guidance to vendors not to trade in prohibited areas
2	Installing signs indicating PKL-free zones
3	Displaying excerpts of relevant articles from the regional regulation prohibiting trading in specific areas

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

Enforcement procedures were also implemented in stages, as shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Warning Stages Issued to Street Vendors

Warning Stage	Response Time Given
First Warning	7 days
Second Warning	7 days
Third Warning	3 days; enforcement conducted if relocation does not occur

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

From the perspective of Van Meter & Van Horn's (1975) policy implementation model, communication constitutes a central variable influencing implementation performance, particularly in ensuring policy clarity, consistency, and transmission accuracy. The findings demonstrate that Satpol PP successfully fulfilled the communication component through intensive socialization, clear warning mechanisms, and structured enforcement stages, reflecting strong inter-organizational coordination and message transmission. However, the persistence of non-compliance among some street vendors highlights the interaction between communication and other implementation variables, particularly socio-economic conditions and implementer responsiveness. Thus, while communication was effectively institutionalized, policy outcomes were moderated by target group characteristics and resource-related constraints, illustrating that successful implementation depends not only on communication intensity but also on the alignment of policy demands with the lived realities of policy targets.

6) Social, economic, and political environment

Policy implementation performance can also be assessed through the extent to which the external environment supports or constrains the achievement of policy objectives. The implementation of the street vendor arrangement policy in Bojonegoro Regency

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experienced notable constraints due to an external environment that was insufficiently conducive. Despite relocation efforts to officially designated areas, a number of vendors returned to their original trading locations, primarily due to economic considerations. This condition indicates that the external environment has not fully supported effective policy implementation.

The external environment dimension in this study encompasses social, economic, and political factors, including economic resources within the community, the level of support or resistance from interest groups, public opinion, and political elite commitment. The findings show that unfavorable social, economic, and political conditions contributed to reduced policy effectiveness.

a. Social environment

The social environment emerged as a major inhibiting factor in policy implementation. Although street vendors were formally relocated to permitted areas, many chose to resume trading in prohibited locations. According to a *Satpol PP* officer responsible for enforcement:

“There are still many vendors who violate the regulation. After enforcement actions are carried out, a number of vendors return to areas that have already been prohibited, citing various reasons.”

From the perspective of the street vendors, economic survival was the dominant rationale for non-compliance. One vendor stated: *“Honestly, I am tired of constantly avoiding enforcement officers, but I am only trying to earn a living for my family. I did not relocate because I am afraid my income would decrease.”*

These accounts demonstrate that social acceptance of the policy remained limited, particularly when compliance was perceived to threaten household livelihoods. Social resistance, therefore, weakened the sustainability of enforcement outcomes.

b. Economic environment

Economic conditions constituted the most dominant external constraint on policy implementation. Many street vendors were reluctant to comply with relocation directives because income at the new trading sites declined significantly, and they were perceived as less strategic and with less customer traffic. One vendor explained:

“The previous location was more strategic and easier for customers to remember. After moving to the new location, my income decreased significantly because there are fewer buyers.”

This economic vulnerability prompted vendors to prioritize income security over regulatory compliance, thereby undermining enforcement consistency.

c. Political environment

The findings indicate that political elites in Bojonegoro Regency did not play a significant role in supporting the implementation of public order and street vendor regulation policies. Political actors neither actively opposed nor strongly advocated for the policy, resulting in limited political backing. This passive stance reduced the policy’s institutional legitimacy and weakened reinforcement efforts at the local level.

To summarize the influence of the external environment on policy implementation, Table 9 presents an overview of key findings across social, economic, and political dimensions.

Table 9. External Environmental Factors Affecting Street Vendor Policy Implementation

Dimension	Key Conditions	Impact on Implementation
Social	Low acceptance of relocation; vendors return to prohibited areas	Weak compliance and recurring violations
Economic	Declining income in relocation sites	Strong resistance to relocation
Political	Limited involvement and support from political elites	Reduced policy reinforcement

Source: Data processed by researchers (2026)

Within the framework of Van Meter & Van Horn (1975), the external environment constitutes a critical variable influencing policy implementation outcomes, particularly through socio-economic conditions, political support, and public response. The findings indicate that the implementation of street vendor regulation in Bojonegoro was constrained by an unsupportive external environment characterized by economic insecurity, limited political endorsement, and social resistance among policy targets. Although enforcement mechanisms were formally in place, unfavorable environmental conditions weakened compliance and reduced policy effectiveness. This confirms Van Meter and Van Horn’s assertion that successful policy implementation is highly contingent upon the alignment between policy objectives and the social, economic, and political contexts in which the policy operates.

Constraints and government efforts in street vendor management

The rapid growth and unregulated distribution of street vendors in Bojonegoro Regency have posed significant challenges to public order, comfort, safety, and traffic management. To address these issues, the local government enacted Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Tranquility, which includes provisions for the management and organization of street vendors, particularly in Bojonegoro District. Effective implementation requires adherence to procedural guidelines to achieve the intended outcomes of orderly and compliant public spaces.

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However, field observations indicate that several constraints hinder full policy implementation. First, there is no designated area that can accommodate all street vendors, limiting the government's ability to relocate them effectively. Second, street vendors have emerged organically over time, making comprehensive management and enforcement challenging. These structural and socio-economic factors complicate the achievement of the policy's objectives, as the available infrastructure and organizational capacity are insufficient to fully control informal economic activities.

In response to these challenges, the local government has undertaken several mitigation efforts. These include continuous enforcement and socialization by the Civil Service Police Unit (*Satpol PP*), provision of guidance and advisory services to vendors, and the establishment of procedural mechanisms for relocating vendors in an orderly manner. Without such proactive measures, the regulation would fail to achieve its goals, and street vendor activity would continue to disrupt public order. By combining regulatory enforcement with advisory and participatory strategies, the government aims to balance policy compliance with the livelihood needs of vendors.

4. CONCLUSION

The findings demonstrate that the implementation of Regional Regulation Number 15 of 2015 on Public Order and Community Tranquility remains only partially effective, despite the existence of a clear regulatory framework and relatively adequate institutional capacity at the local level. Policy standards and objectives are clearly articulated and consistently understood by implementers, with *Satpol PP* conducting systematic socialization and enforcement activities supported by sufficient human and financial resources, a structured organizational arrangement, and a generally positive implementer disposition. Inter-organizational communication between enforcement officers and street vendors has been institutionalized through repeated advisories, warning mechanisms, and staged enforcement procedures, reflecting a strong administrative effort to translate policy goals into practice. Nevertheless, these institutional strengths have proven insufficient to overcome significant external constraints, as the social, economic, and political environment emerged as the most critical limiting factor in policy implementation. Economic insecurity among street vendors—particularly declining income following relocation—undermines compliance and drives recurring violations, while limited political engagement weakens policy reinforcement and social resistance reflects a misalignment between regulatory objectives and the lived realities of policy targets. These findings corroborate Van Meter and Van Horn's argument that successful policy implementation depends not only on administrative capacity and communication but also on the compatibility of policy demands with broader socio-economic and political contexts. This study is limited by its qualitative descriptive design and single-regency focus, which restricts generalizability, its reliance on interviews and observations without quantitative measurement of policy outcomes, and its emphasis on implementers' and vendors' perspectives to the relative exclusion of other stakeholders. Future research should therefore adopt comparative or mixed-methods approaches across multiple regions, integrate quantitative assessments of socio-economic and spatial outcomes, and further examine the roles of political leadership, inter-sectoral collaboration, and participatory policy design, as well as alternative policy instruments such as incentive-based regulation and inclusive urban planning, to advance more equitable and sustainable public order policy implementation within decentralized governance systems.

REFERENCES

- 1) Agustino, L. (2006). *Dasar-dasar Kebijaksanaan Publik*. Bandung: CV. Alfabeta.
- 2) Akintola, A., Birch, D. N., & Kilinc, S. (2024). Bridging the gap between research evidence and its implementation in public health practice: case studies of embedded research model. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1299), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-18727-z>
- 3) Anwar, F. Y. (2024). The Role of Street Vendors in Local Economic Development: Exploring Their Contribution to Regional Economy. *Journal of Social Research*, 4(1), 1–6.
- 4) Aulia, A. P. (2025). *The Dilemma of Decentralization in Public Policy Implementation in Indonesia*. 2(4), 1–13.
- 5) Budijaya, M. I., & Heryanto, Y. (2024). The Impact of Regional Autonomy on Regional Development. *International Journal of Social Service and Research*, 4(9), 1–6.
- 6) Chand, S. (2025). Methods of Data Collection in Qualitative Research: Interviews, Focus Groups, Observations, and Document Analysis. *Advances in Educational Research and Evaluation*, 6, 303–317. <https://doi.org/10.25082/AERE.2025.01.001>
- 7) Faguet, J.-P. (2014). Decentralization and Governance. *World Development*, 53, 2–13. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2013.01.002>
- 8) Hidayat, A. R., Hospes, O., & Termeer, C. J. A. M. (2025). Why Democratization and Decentralization in Indonesia Have Mixed Results on the Ground: A Systematic Literature Review. *Public Administration and Development*, 45(2), 159–172. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/pad.2095>

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- 9) Hidayatulloh, B., & Murdoko, M. (2025). The Role of Regional Regulations in Optimizing Public Order, Public Order, and Community Protection. *TATOHI: Jurnal Ilmu Hukum*, 5, 475. <https://doi.org/10.47268/tatohi.v5i110.3542>
- 10) Hoesein, Z. A., & Rahayu, S. D. (2022). *The Effectiveness of Decentralization Policy in Local Government Administration*. 9(1), 242–259.
- 11) Kurniawan, I., Djunaedi, O., & Akkapin, S. (2024). The Application of the Principle of Decentralisation in Regional Autonomy. *Sibatik Journal*, 3(12), 1301–1308.
- 12) Lim, W. M. (2025). *What Is Qualitative Research ? An Overview and Guidelines*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14413582241264619>
- 13) Miles, M. B., Huberman, A. M., & Saldana, J. (2014). *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Methods Sourcebook*.
- 14) Moleong, L. J. (2012). Metodologi penelitian kualitatif, Bandung. *Pariwisata Pedesaan Sebagai Alternatif Pembangunan Berkelanjutan (Laporan Penelitian Hibah Bersaing Perguruan Tinggi) Yogyakarta*.
- 15) Permana, H., Astiti, P., Melati, D., Riwayanti, J., Ginanjar, S. E., Publik, A., & Lima, P. K. (2023). Implementasi Kebijakan Penertiban Pedagang Kaki Lima di Kota Bandung. *Dinamika : Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Administrasi Negara*, 10(1), 737–746.
- 16) Rahayu, W. N. I., Sawir, M., Melawati, F., & Mu'is, A. (2025). Social Sciences & Humanities Open The public space Paradox : Balancing governance and street vending in urban Indonesia. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 11(April), 101559. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2025.101559>
- 17) Sattuo, M., Maskawati, M., & Aboalela, N. H. F. (2025). Evaluation of Regional Policy Regarding Street Vendors : A Case Study of Bone Regency from the Perspective of. *Constitutional Law Review*, 4(1), 32–53.
- 18) Shrestha, K., & Hankla, C. R. (2025). *Decentralization in Theory and Practice : A Comprehensive*.
- 19) Smoke, P. (2015). Managing Public Sector Decentralization in Developing Countries: Moving Beyond Conventional Recipes. *Public Administration and Development*, 35, 250–262. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pad.1736>
- 20) Sugiyono. (2022). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif dan R&D*.
- 21) Syaprianto, S., Afrizal, A., & Siska, L. T. (2023). Implementation of Pekanbaru City Policy Public Order and Community Tranquility. *Jurnal Kajian Pemerintah*, 10(2), 81–87.
- 22) Usman, S. (2002). *Regional Autonomy in Indonesia : Field Experiences and Emerging Challenges* (Issue June).
- 23) Van Meter, Donald S, & Van Horn, Carl E. (1975). The Policy Implementation Process: A Conceptual Framework. *Administration & Society*, 6(4), 445–488. <https://doi.org/10.1177/009539977500600404>
- 24) Wicaksono, H. N. (2016). Analisis Implementasi Peraturan Daerah Kabupaten Nganjur Nomer 8 Tahun 2013 tentang Penyelenggaraan Ketertiban Umum (Studi Kasus pada Pengemis, Pengamen, Pedagang Asongan dan Pengelap Mobil di Kecamatan Kertosono Kabupaten Nganjuk). *Jurnal PUBLIKA*, 4(1), 1–15.
- 25) Wiyoto, A. A. (2024). Implementasi Kebijakan Penataan Pedagang Kaki Lima di Taman Bungkul Surabaya. *Jurnal Ilmu Sosial Dan Ilmu Politik*, 4(2), 121–132.